

Studies on the Complexes of Some Basic Dyes with Hexacyanoferrates

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Basic dyes like bismarck brown, crystal violet, methyl violet and methylene blue react with potassium hexacyanoferrate (II) and (III) and ferro- and ferricyanic acids to give water insoluble products. Bismarck brown forms 1:1 complexes while all other dyes give 3:1 products. Infrared studies show that bismarck brown undergoes protonation of the NH_2 group during complex formation and the $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ frequency appears as a doublet, which may be explained on the basis of unsymmetrical hydrogen bonding. In the case of other dyes the reaction product is obtained through electrostatic interaction of the cationic moiety of the dye with the anionic metal complex.

INSPITE of the fact that such properties of pigments as fastness, penetrating power, absorbability etc. are greatly influenced by reactions with metals, the reaction of dyes with metal complexes has not drawn much attention so far. Recently Warwick and Witham¹ prepared some basic dye complexes with copper ferrocyanide and suggested their possible use in oil base letter press, lithographic, water reducible letter press and liquid inks but made no studies on the nature of these complexes. In this paper studies have thus been carried out on the complex formation between some basic dyes and hexacyanoferrates.

Experimental

Reagents :

Potassium hexacyanoferrate (II) and (III) were AnalaR grade (BDH) reagents. Ferro- and ferricyanic acids were prepared from potassium hexacyanoferrate (II) and (III) by the ion exchange method using a cation exchange resin, amberlite IR-120.

The basic dyes, bismarck brown, methylene blue, crystal violet and methyl violet were BDH products and were recrystallised from 50 per cent ethanol before use. Their purity was checked by thin layer chromatography and were found to give a single spot.

Equipment :

For conductometric titrations, Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge CLO1/OIA (India), using a dip type cell was used. Amperometric titrations were carried out on a Cambridge pen recording polarograph using a H-type cell², a saturated calomel electrode and a dropping mercury electrode.

Infrared spectra of the basic dye complexes were recorded on Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer in KBr discs.

Conductometric titration :

The following sets were prepared for both direct (dye in the cell) and reverse (ferro- and ferricyanic acids and potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) and (III) in the cell) titrations :

- (i) 30.0 ml of 0.001M dyes titrated with 0.01M hexacyanoferrates.
- (ii) 30.0 ml of 0.001M hexacyanoferrates titrated with 0.01M dyes.

A curve was plotted between the conductance and the volume of the titrant added and the stoichiometric ratio was found from the inflexion point of the curve.

Amperometric titration :

The titrations were carried out at a constant potential of -0.4 volt (plateau of the hexacyanoferrates) in 0.1N H_2SO_4 as supporting electrolyte³. The following sets were prepared.

- (i) 1.0 ml of 0.01M hexacyanoferrates + 1.0 ml of 1.0N H_2SO_4 + 8.0 ml H_2O titrated with 0.01M dyes.

A curve was plotted between current and volume of the titrant added and the combining ratio was found from the inflexion point.

Preparation of the Complexes :

An aqueous solution of ferrocyanic acid, ferricyanic acid, potassium ferrocyanide or potassium ferricyanide (0.005M) was mixed slowly with an aqueous solution of the dye (0.005M), in their stoichiometric ratio, with constant stirring. A precipitate was obtained at once which was filtered off by suction and washed liberally with water till free from any unreacted dye or the

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cyanide complex. The product was then washed with alcohol, then ether and finally dried in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Results and Discussion

Amperometric and conductometric (both direct and reverse) titrations were carried out to determine the composition of the complexes formed and it is concluded from these titrations that bismarck brown forms 1:1 complex with potassium hexacyanoferrate (II) and (III) as well as ferro- and ferricyanic acids. On the other hand, methylene blue, crystal violet and methyl violet form 3:1 complexes (dye : complex cyanide). The formulae of these complexes were established on the basis of elemental analysis (Table).

Infrared studies :

In all the complexes, the O-H symmetric and asymmetric stretching bands and H-O-H bands appear in the range 3300-3500 cm⁻¹ and 1600-1640 cm⁻¹ respectively showing the presence of water of crystallisation.

Complexes of bismarck brown :

Potassium hexacyanoferrate (II) and (III) show only one C≡N stretching band at 2020 and 2110 cm⁻¹

respectively while their respective acids give two bands at 2070 and 2095 cm⁻¹ which has been explained⁴⁻¹² on the basis of unsymmetrical hydrogen bonding between the hydrogen atoms of the acid and the nitrogen of the cyanide group. The C≡N stretching frequency in bismarck brown complexes is observed as a doublet in the range 2020-2100 cm⁻¹.

The N-H symmetric and asymmetric stretching bands due to NH₂ group of bismarck brown appear in the range 3400-3500 cm⁻¹. But on interaction with metal cyanides, in addition, a fresh band also appears at a lower frequency, viz., 3160-3200 cm⁻¹. The appearance of these new bands can be attributed to the protonation of the amino group to form NH₃⁺. The NH₂ deformation band at 1640 cm⁻¹ due to amino group in bismarck brown also shifts to lower frequency and overlaps with the broad band due to water of crystallisation at 1630 cm⁻¹. This observation further confirms the protonation of the amine group in the bismarck brown-metal cyanide complexes. The presence of a band around 3300 cm⁻¹ due to -NH₂ group shows that in the complex, both the amine and the protonated NH₃⁺ groups are present. The presence of both the NH₂ and NH₃⁺ groups may be due to the fact that

TABLE—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	H ₂ O%		Fe%		C%		N%		H%	
	Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found
1. H ₂ [Fe(CN) ₆][C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆].4.0H ₂ O	11.37	10.99	8.85	8.75	45.50	45.64	30.96	30.73	3.95	4.14
2. H ₄ [Fe(CN) ₆][C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆].4.0H ₂ O	11.36	11.54	8.83	8.79	45.43	45.63	30.93	30.69	4.10	3.99
3. K ₂ H[Fe(CN) ₆][C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆].3.5H ₂ O	9.00	9.13	8.00	7.79	41.14	41.81	28.00	27.92	3.14	3.24
4. K ₂ H[Fe(CN) ₆][C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆].4.0H ₂ O	9.62	9.71	7.48	7.67	38.50	39.14	26.20	26.69	3.07	3.17
5. ‡[Fe(CN) ₆][C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆ S].4.5H ₂ O	7.26	7.19	5.02	4.88	58.11	57.80	18.83	18.48	5.65	5.73
6. H[Fe(CN) ₆][C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆ S].4.0H ₂ O	6.50	6.47	5.05	4.91	58.53	58.11	18.97	18.89	5.60	5.55
7. *[Fe(CN) ₆][C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆ S].5.5H ₂ O	8.73	8.46	4.94	4.87	57.19	57.01	18.53	18.36	5.73	5.57
8. K[Fe(CN) ₆][C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆ S].4.5H ₂ O	7.01	6.90	4.85	4.80	56.15	56.13	18.19	18.23	5.45	5.40
9. ‡[Fe(CN) ₆][C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₈ S].5.0H ₂ O	6.34	6.55	3.94	3.87	68.54	68.44	14.80	14.71	7.05	6.99
10. H[Fe(CN) ₆][C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₈].9.0H ₂ O	10.86	10.96	3.75	3.69	65.19	65.51	14.08	14.20	7.31	7.21
11. *[Fe(CN) ₆][C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₈].4.5H ₂ O	5.74	5.86	3.97	3.85	68.98	68.78	14.90	14.50	7.02	6.99
12. K[Fe(CN) ₆][C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₈].7.0H ₂ O	8.43	8.44	3.75	3.72	65.10	65.22	14.06	14.01	6.96	7.00
13. ‡[Fe(CN) ₆][C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₈].7.0H ₂ O	8.92	9.05	3.96	3.82	66.28	65.87	14.87	14.86	6.94	6.84
14. H[Fe(CN) ₆][C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₈].10.0H ₂ O	12.26	12.00	3.81	3.77	63.80	63.29	14.31	14.52	7.15	6.99
15. *[Fe(CN) ₆][C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₈].3.0H ₂ O	4.02	4.28	4.17	4.01	69.85	69.87	15.67	15.72	6.71	6.55
16. K[Fe(CN) ₆][C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₈].6.0H ₂ O	7.53	7.38	3.90	3.80	65.31	65.01	14.65	14.39	6.69	6.88

‡ Complexes formed from H₂(Fe(CN)₆)

* Complexes formed from K₂Fe(CN)₆

bismarck brown has four amine groups and only one NH_2 group is protonated and rest of the three remain unchanged.

Thus the interaction of the bismarck brown with ferro- and ferricyanic acids and potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) and (III) is taking place through unsymmetrical hydrogen bonding, N-H...N, between the nitrogen of the cyanide group and the proton of the amine of the bismarck brown.

Complexes of cationic dyes :

In all the cationic dyes all the important bands appear at the same frequency on complex formation. This means that the reaction with these dyes does not take place through protonation. The complexes isolated with these dyes may, therefore, be considered to have been formed through electrostatic interaction between the cationic moiety of the dye and anionic metal complex.

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